

Mathematical Foundations and Group Theory Applications in the CFOP Method for Solving Rubik's Cube

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the mathematical principles underlying the CFOP method for solving the Rubik's Cube, with a particular focus on the concepts of conjugation and commutators from group theory. The CFOP method, developed by Jessica Fridrich, is one of the most efficient techniques for solving the Rubik's Cube, breaking the solution process into four distinct stages: Cross, F2L (First Two Layers), OLL (Orientation of the Last Layer), and PLL (Permutation of the Last Layer). We begin by providing a historical overview of the Rubik's Cube, followed by definitions of key concepts in group theory. We then demonstrate that the set of all possible Rubik's Cube moves forms a group under the operation of composition, satisfying the properties of closure, associativity, identity, and inverse. Through detailed examples, we illustrate how each step of the CFOP method can be achieved using conjugation and commutators, highlighting their role in simplifying the solving process and maintaining the overall structure of the cube.

While the focus is primarily on the CFOP method, the paper acknowledges other solving methods and advanced techniques that were not covered in detail. Future work could explore these areas further, expanding on the foundational concepts presented here. By mastering the principles of group theory, cubers can enhance their solving strategies, achieve faster solve times, and gain a deeper appreciation for the mathematical beauty of the Rubik's Cube.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Rubik's Cube

The Rubik's Cube, originally invented in 1974 by Ernő Rubik (Reese, 2020), a Hungarian architecture professor at the Academy of Applied Arts and Design (Bellis, 2019), has become popular since then. It consists of a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ arrangement of smaller cubes, each with one of six solid colors on each face. The goal of the puzzle is to manipulate the cube to return it to its original state, where each face of the cube has only one color.

The Rubik's Cube gained international fame in the 1980s and has remained a beloved and challenging puzzle for enthusiasts of all ages (Reese, 2020). Its popularity has spurred various competitions, with participants aiming to solve the cube in the shortest time possible. Additionally, the Rubik's Cube has inspired numerous variations, including different $n \times n$ variants and different shape variants (McFadden, 2021) highlighting its enduring impact on the world of puzzles and problem-solving.

One problem may arise when one thinks about the original solution of this three-dimensional puzzle: how do people explain their solutions?

1.2 CFOP Method

The CFOP method, also known as the Fridrich method, is one of the most popular and efficient techniques for solving Rubik's Cube (Makisumi, 2007). This method revolutionized speedcubing by providing a systematic approach that breaks the solution process into four distinct stages: Cross, F2L (First Two Layers), OLL (Orientation of the Last Layer), and PLL (Permutation of the Last Layer) (Desai et al., 2020). Each stage addresses a specific part of the puzzle, allowing cubers to solve the cube in a more structured and time-efficient manner.

- Cross: The first step involves solving the edge pieces of one face to form a cross. This step is crucial as it sets the foundation for the rest of the solve, and experienced cubers aim to complete it with minimal moves and maximum efficiency.
- F2L (First Two Layers): In this stage, pairs of corner and edge pieces are simultaneously inserted into their correct positions in the first two layers of the cube. F2L is the most complex and variable stage of the CFOP method, requiring a deep understanding of cube algorithms and intuitive solving techniques.
- OLL (Orientation of the Last Layer): Once the first two layers are solved, the next step is to orient all the pieces of the last layer so that they match the correct colors on the top face. OLL involves memorizing and executing one of 57 different algorithms to achieve the desired orientation.
- PLL (Permutation of the Last Layer): The final step is to permute the pieces of the last layer so that each piece is in its correct position. This stage involves 21 different

algorithms that rearrange the pieces without disturbing their orientation, ultimately solving the cube.

The CFOP method's structured approach and reliance on memorized algorithms make it a favorite among competitive speedcubers. Its efficiency and effectiveness have led to numerous world record solves, cementing its status as the go-to method for those aiming to achieve fast solve times. In 2015, Lucas Etter set the record for a standard cube to 4.9 seconds, the first time under 5 seconds ("Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik's Cube", 2024). In 2018, Yusheng Du set the new record to 3.47 seconds, which was believed to be unbeatable. By mastering the CFOP method, cubers can significantly reduce their solve times and improve their performance in speedcubing competitions.

2. HISTORY

The Rubik's Cube, created by Hungarian architect Ernő Rubik in 1974, began as an educational tool designed to help his students grasp three-dimensional geometry (Reese, 2020). Originally named the "Magic Cube," it was patented in Hungary in 1975 and appeared in local toy stores by 1977 ("Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik's Cube", 2024). The cube's intricate mechanism, allowing independent rotation of its smaller cubes while maintaining the overall structure ("Exploring the Mechanics: How Do Rubik's Cubes Work", 2023), presented a captivating challenge not only for Rubik but for anyone who attempted to solve it.

The Magic Cube's international breakthrough came in 1979 when it was showcased at global toy fairs ("Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik's Cube", 2024). Recognizing its potential, Tom Kremer, a toy expert, brokered a deal with Ideal Toy Corporation to distribute it worldwide (Smith, 2014). Rebranded as the "Rubik's Cube," it was launched globally in 1980 and quickly captivated a global audience, becoming a cultural icon of the 1980s. By 1982, over 100 million units had been sold (Smith, 2014), and the first Rubik's Cube World Championship was held in Budapest ("Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik's Cube", 2024), marking the beginning of organized competitive cubing.

Despite a decline in popularity in the late 1980s, the cube experienced a resurgence in the 2000s with the rise of speedcubing (Reese, 2020). This new competitive aspect saw participants solving

the cube in record times, leading to a revitalized interest and numerous international competitions. In 2018, the Red Bull Rubik's Cube World Championship was introduced (“Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik’s Cube”, 2024), reflecting the cube's enduring appeal.

Throughout its history, the Rubik's Cube has celebrated significant milestones, including its 40th and 50th anniversaries (“Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik’s Cube”, 2024), and witnessed record-breaking achievements, such as Max Park's single solve time of 3.13 seconds in 2023 (“Important Dates and Timeline of the Rubik’s Cube”, 2024). Today, it continues to be a beloved puzzle, educational tool, and competitive sport, maintaining its status as a symbol of intellectual challenge and creativity.

3. RELATED WORK

The study of the Rubik's Cube from a mathematical perspective has been explored extensively over the years, with significant contributions from various researchers and institutions. This section reviews key works related to the mathematical analysis and solving techniques of the Rubik's Cube.

Group theory provides a robust framework for understanding the Rubik's Cube, as it captures the cube's structure and the effects of different moves. In his seminal work, David Singmaster introduced notation and theoretical insights that laid the foundation for later mathematical studies on the Rubik's Cube (Singmaster, 1981). Singmaster's contributions include the standard cube notation and the identification of cube moves as elements of a permutation group.

A comprehensive study conducted by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) delves deeply into the mathematical properties of the Rubik's Cube. The paper titled *The Mathematics of the Rubik's Cube* discusses the application of group theory, combinatorics, and permutation theory to solve and analyze the cube (Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2006). The study provides a thorough examination of the cube's symmetry, the order of permutations, and the concept of God's Number, which represents the maximum number of moves required to solve the cube from any given configuration.

Additional research has focused on the combinatorial aspects of the Rubik's Cube. Berlekamp, Conway, and Guy's *Winning Ways for Your Mathematical Plays* includes an analysis of the cube's combinatorial complexity, exploring the vast number of possible configurations and strategies for solving the cube efficiently (Berlekamp & Conway & Guy, 1982). Their work emphasizes the importance of understanding the cube's underlying mathematical structure to develop efficient solving algorithms.

The advent of computational power has enabled more sophisticated analysis and solving techniques. Kociemba's algorithm, for example, significantly reduced the number of moves required to solve the Rubik's Cube by employing advanced computational methods and heuristic search strategies (Kociemba, 1992). Kociemba's work has been instrumental in competitive speedcubing, where solving efficiency is paramount.

The Rubik's Cube has also been utilized as an educational tool to teach abstract algebra and group theory. Researchers have developed curricula and instructional materials that leverage the cube's properties to illustrate fundamental mathematical concepts. These educational initiatives highlight the Rubik's Cube's value beyond recreational solving, demonstrating its applicability in academic settings.

Several online platforms and communities have contributed to the collective understanding and solving techniques of the Rubik's Cube. Websites such as Ruwix and Speedsolving.com provide extensive resources, including solving guides, algorithm databases, and forums for discussion ("Speedsolving Puzzles Community.", 2024). These resources are invaluable for both beginners and advanced cubers seeking to deepen their knowledge and improve their solving skills.

4. DEFINITIONS

Before we dive into the solutions of Rubik's Cube, we need to have some definitions for the mathematics we need to use later on.

4.1 Group Theory

Group theory is a branch of abstract algebra that studies the algebraic structures known as groups. A group is defined as a set of elements combined with a binary operator that satisfies four fundamental properties: closure, associativity, identity, and inverse. Suppose there is a group G under the binary operation \cdot , represented as (G, \cdot) .

1. *Closure*: For any two elements $a, b \in G$, the result of the operation $a \cdot b \in G$.
2. *Associativity*: For any three elements $a, b, c \in G$, the equation $(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c)$ holds.
3. *Identity*: There exists an element $e \in G$ such that for every element $a \in G$, the equation $e \cdot a = a \cdot e = a$ holds.
4. *Inverse*: For each element $a \in G$, there exists an element $b \in G$ such that $a \cdot b = b \cdot a = e$, where e is the identity element.

4.2 Conjugation

Conjugation is an operation in which an element $a \in G$ is transformed by another element $g \in G$ through the conjugation operation. The conjugate of a by g is defined as:

$$a^g = g a g^{-1}$$

Conjugation is usually used to understand how elements in a group interact with each other under inner automorphisms. It helps in studying the structure of subgroups, normal subgroups, and in classifying elements by their conjugacy classes. For the sake of Rubik's Cube, we do not need to know its application in these fields here.

4.3 Commutator

The commutator of two elements a and b in a group G is defined as:

$$[a, b] = a b a^{-1} b^{-1}$$

Commutators measure the "non-commutativity" of two elements. If $[a, b] = e$ (the identity element), a and b commute. Commutators are crucial in the study of derived subgroups, and they play a significant role in various areas of algebra, including Lie algebras and differential geometry. The same as above, we do not need to know its applications in these fields for our understanding.

If moves X and Y affect a few (ideally less than 3) of the same pieces, we can say that they "almost" commute. Thus, $[X, Y]$ would alter only a few pieces, leaving the majority of the cube unchanged. This is useful when the cube is almost solved. If there is a single unique piece that is permuted by both X and Y , then we can say $[X, Y]$ is a three-cycle i.e. there is a piece a such that $XYX^{-1}Y^{-1}$ maps pieces a to b , b to c , and c to a , and does not move any other piece (Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2006).

4.4 Rubik's Cube Notation

Before connecting a Rubik's Cube to a group, we need to define moves on the Rubik's Cube. To represent the moves on the Rubik's Cube, the following standard notation is used:

- R : 90-degree clockwise rotation of the right face.
- L : 90-degree clockwise rotation of the left face.
- U : 90-degree clockwise rotation of the upper face.
- D : 90-degree clockwise rotation of the down face.
- F : 90-degree clockwise rotation of the front face.
- B : 90-degree clockwise rotation of the back face.

Figure 1

This notation is used to describe sequences of moves that solve or manipulate the Rubik's Cube. For simplicity, we write the *inverse* of a move X as X' . For example, the sequence $RUR'U'$ represents a common maneuver known as the *right-hand algorithm*, which is often used in the CFOP method to manipulate the last layer of the cube.

4.5 Cube Orientation

For convenience for understanding, we define F as turning *Green* face clockwise, U as turning *yellow* face clockwise.

5. THEOREMS

Theorem 1. The set of all possible Rubik's Cube moves forms a group under the operation of composition.

Proof. To show that the set of Rubik's Cube moves forms a group, we need to verify the following four properties: closure, associativity, identity, and inverse. We will prove each property using a separate lemma.

Lemma 1. The set of Rubik's Cube moves is closed under composition.

Proof. Let a and b be any two moves in the set of Rubik's Cube moves. The composition $a \cdot b$ represents performing move a followed by move b . Since performing two legal moves in sequence results in another legal move, $a \cdot b$ is also a move in the set. Therefore, the set is closed under composition.

Lemma 2. The set of Rubik's Cube moves is associative under composition.

Proof. Let a, b, c be any three moves in the set of Rubik's Cube moves. The composition of these moves satisfies associativity if $(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c)$. Since the physical manipulation of the cube does not depend on the grouping of moves, the result of applying the moves is the same regardless of how they are grouped. Thus, associativity holds.

Lemma 3. There exists an identity element in the set of Rubik's Cube moves.

Proof. There exists an identity move e in the set of Rubik's Cube moves, which corresponds to doing nothing to the cube. For any move a , applying e before or after a leaves a unchanged: $e \cdot a = a \cdot e = a$. Therefore, e is the identity element in the group.

Lemma 4. Every move in the set of Rubik's Cube moves has an inverse.

Proof. For each move a in the set of Rubik's Cube moves, there exists an inverse move a^{-1} that undoes a . When a is followed by a^{-1} , the cube returns to its original state:

$a \cdot a^{-1} = a^{-1} \cdot a = e$, where e is the identity move. Thus, every move has an inverse in the set.

Since the set of Rubik's Cube moves satisfies closure, associativity, identity, and inverse, we conclude that it forms a group under the operation of composition.

5.1 Inverse

Notice that the inverse of the moves on the cube follows the "socks-shoes" property, i.e.

$(XY)^{-1} = Y^{-1}X^{-1}$. After defining the moves on the Rubik's Cube as a group under composition, we can dive deep into the mathematical aspect of the CFOP method.

5.2 Cross

According to our definition, we are making a cross on the white face using the four edge pieces. Figure 2 shows the finished "cross".

Figure 2

For the most part, this part only involves fitting the right edges into the right place. In some scenarios, it is necessary to use *conjugation* to complete this step.

5.2.1 Example 1

Figure 3

To complete the cross below by fitting the label 1 edge piece to label 2 piece, we need to apply the following moves,

$$F'LF$$

which is a conjugate to $L \in G$. In this way, the “action move” L moves the piece to the right position, while moves F' and F help to bring the correct piece to the right position before the “action move”, and help fix whatever is messed up after applying the “action move”. This is the main application of conjugation in the “Cross” section, which helps moving the right piece and fixing the rest.

5.3 F2L(First 2 Layers)

After completing the Cross, we need to fix the first two layers. One common way to complete F2L is to set up the *F2L pair* first, and then insert the pair in the right position. In Figure 4, the *F2L pair* is the connected edge pieces with colors *orange* and *green*, and the corner pieces with colors *white*, *orange*, and *green*.

Figure 4

Conjugation and commutator can help in both steps.

5.3.1 Example 2

Figure 5

In Figure 5, we are trying to connect pieces labeled with 1 and 2 to make up a *F2L pair*. We can do the following to complete,

$$F'U'F$$

which is a conjugate to $U' \in G$. Then, we can apply the following moves to complete insertion,

$$U'U'R'UR$$

which latter part is a commutator for $U, R \in G$. So the combined moves are the following,

$$(F'U'F)U'(U'R'UR)$$

which is a combination of conjugation, commutator, and intermediate moves. In this example, the conjugation helps connect the *F2L pair*, which brings the right pieces to the right position for cycling, while the commutator helps insert the pair into the right position.

5.3.2 Example 3

Figure 6

In this example, we want to connect piece 1 with piece 2 to make a *F2L pair*. We can do the following move to connect them first,

$$LUL'$$

which is a conjugate to $U \in G$. Then we can use the following to insert it to the right position,

$$ULU'L'$$

which is a commutator. So, the completed moves are,

$$(LUL')(ULU'L')$$

which is a combination of conjugation and commutator. Notice that conjugations are usually used to direct the pieces to the right position as above, and then a combination of commutators and conjugations and some intermediate moves are used for the pairing and insertion.

5.4 OLL(Orientation of Last Layer)

In OLL, commutators have many more uses, since we are trying to maintain what we have completed in the previous steps but cycle the above pieces. Sometimes, commutators are used in combination with conjugation.

5.4.1 Example 4

Figure 7

In figure 7, we are essentially trying to fix the yellow face. The following set of moves fixes it,

$$R'U'RUR'UUR$$

Notice that we can group it as following,

$$R'U'(RUR'U)UR = R'U'[R', U]UR$$

This becomes a conjugate of a commutator $[R', U] \in G$. This is a great example to see the roles of conjugate and commutators: commutators help cycle the pieces, and conjugation helps bring the right pieces to cycle, and then bringing them back.

5.4.2 Example 5

Figure 8

To fix the orientation of the last layer, we can use the following moves,

$$FR'F'RURU'R'$$

After grouping the moves, we have,

$$(FR'F'R)(URU'R') = [F, R'][U, R]$$

This is a combination of two commutators. The whole algorithm consists of 2 transpositions of corner pieces and a 3-cycle of edge pieces.

5.4.3 Example 6

Figure 9

The following set of moves fixes the orientation of the last layer,

$$R'U'R'FRF'R'FRF'UR$$

Notice that we can group it as follows,

$$R'U'(R'FRF')(R'FRF')UR = R'U'[R',F][R',F]UR$$

This becomes a conjugate of two identical combined commutators, $[R', F] \in G$. The commutators do the cycling of the pieces while the conjugation brings the right pieces for cycling, then bring them back to their original positions.

5.5 PLL(Permutation of Last Layer)

To orient the permutation of the last layer, there would be many instances of commutators for the 3-cycles. This includes cycling the edge pieces and corner pieces.

5.5.1 Example 7

Figure 10

To fix the cube, we need the following movements:

$$FFUMUUM'UFF$$

If we rewrite it a bit, we have the following. Notice that M means moving the middle set of cubes clockwise looking from the right,

$$FFUMUUM'UFF = (FFU)MUUM'UU(U'FF) = (FFU)[M, UU](U'FF)$$

Also notice that the inverse of move XX is itself, because $XXXX = e$, multiply by $(XX)^{-1}$ to both sides, we have $XX = (XX)^{-1}$.

So, this becomes a conjugate of the commutator $[M, UU] \in G$. If we only do the moves of the commutator, it is a 3-cycle of three edge pieces but not the three we want to cycle; the conjugation move FFU , $U'FF$ brings the right pieces to desire positions and cycle them through the commutator.

5.5.2 Example 8

Figure 11

To fix it, we need the following movements:

$$UF'LF'RRFL'F'RRFF$$

Regrouping, we have,

$$UF'LF'RRFL'F'RRFF = U(FF)(FLF'RRFL'F'RR)(FF) = U(FF)[FLF', RR](FF)$$

The U move at the start will fix the orientation to accommodate the algorithm, and then we see another instance of conjugation of the commutator, $[FLF', RR] \in G$. Notice that the first element of the commutator is another conjugation of movement $L \in G$. If we only perform the commutator $[FLF', RR]$, we have a 3-cycle of corner pieces but not in the desired positions; again, the conjugation helps cycle the correct pieces.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND FUTURE WORK

While this paper has provided a comprehensive overview of how group theory applies to solving the Rubik's Cube using the CFOP method, there are several areas that were not covered in detail. These areas include:

- **Advanced Cube Notations:** We did not delve into advanced notations such as the use of wide moves, rotations, or slice moves, which are often used in more advanced solving techniques.
- **Alternative Solving Methods:** The focus was primarily on the CFOP method, but there are other popular solving methods such as Roux, ZZ, and Petrus, which also have interesting mathematical properties and applications.
- **Detailed Algorithm Derivation:** Although we provided several examples of how OLL and PLL algorithms can be derived using conjugation and commutators, a more thorough derivation of all 57 OLL algorithms and 21 PLL algorithms was beyond the scope of this paper.

- **Speedcubing Techniques:** Techniques specific to speedcubing, such as lookahead, finger tricks, and the use of inspection time, were not discussed. These techniques, while crucial for competitive solving, are more practical in nature and less focused on the underlying mathematical theory.
- **Higher Order Cubes:** This paper focused on the standard 3x3x3 Rubik's Cube. Higher order cubes, such as the 4x4x4 (Rubik's Revenge) and 5x5x5 (Professor's Cube), introduce additional layers of complexity and interesting mathematical challenges that were not addressed.

Future work could explore these areas in more detail, expanding on the foundational concepts presented in this paper. Additionally, further research could investigate the application of other branches of mathematics, such as combinatorics and graph theory, to the study of Rubik's Cube solving methods.

7. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have explored the mathematical principles underlying the CFOP method for solving the Rubik's Cube, with a particular focus on the concepts of conjugation and commutators from group theory. By demonstrating how each step of the CFOP method—Cross, F2L, OLL, and PLL—can be achieved using these mathematical tools, we have highlighted the powerful role that group theory plays in understanding and solving the Rubik's Cube.

We began by establishing that the set of all possible Rubik's Cube moves forms a group under the operation of composition, satisfying the properties of closure, associativity, identity, and inverse. This foundational result allowed us to delve deeper into the application of group theory in the context of the Rubik's Cube through exploring other group properties.

Through detailed examples, we illustrated how conjugation and commutators can be used to manipulate specific pieces of the cube while maintaining the overall structure. Conjugation helps set up the cube to bring the correct pieces into position, while commutators execute precise cycles of pieces, making them invaluable tools for solving the cube, mainly the OLL and PLL cases efficiently.

The ability to decompose complex algorithms into combinations of conjugations and commutators not only simplifies the solving process but also provides a deeper understanding of the cube's underlying structure. At the same time, through fixing the cube using these two powerful tools, the fixing process is simplified as well. This approach aligns with the broader goals of abstract algebra, where group theory serves as a powerful framework for studying symmetry and transformations.

In conclusion, the CFOP method's heavy reliance on group theory principles underscores the elegance and effectiveness of mathematical problem-solving techniques. By mastering these concepts, cubers can enhance their solving strategies, achieve faster solving times, and gain a greater appreciation for the mathematical beauty of the Rubik's Cube.

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